

Composite particle boards from Date-Palm Leaves – A viable substitute of wood/plywood products

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Manuscript received 6 January 2009, revised 31 March 2009, accepted 1 April 2009

Abstract : Particle board is a good substitute for costly wood/plywood boards. Particle board can be developed from Date-Palm Leaves (DPL), the annually renewable agro waste. DPL have higher ultimate fibre length (1.25–2.50 mm) and α -cellulose content (about 60%) is higher than hard wood/plywood and jute stick. Work of adhesion (contact angle) values between DPL and polymer binder (synthetic and natural) is very low. The impact strength of DPL board is much higher than wood/plywood and jute stick (JS) particle board. The moisture content (%), swelling (%) of DPL board in water is much lower (better) than wood/plywood and JS particle board. During development of DPL particle board, 1.5% water repellent chemical was used to make DPL board water proof. Based on these pertinent findings, DPL particle boards (size 2' \times 2' \times ½') were developed and used as false ceilings. The cost of DPL particle board is about 30% of the cost of wood/plywood boards.

Keywords : Date-Palm Leaves, particle board, properties, wood substitutes, eco-friendly.

Introduction

With the change in the global scenario, wood resources are continuously depleting while the demand is increasing day by day. With a view to conserve the forest resource and consequent shortage of wood, the existing wood, plywood, fibre board can't meet the increasing demand both for industry and in domestic field. Currently present yearly requirement of wood in India is 31 million cubic meters. The estimated production is only 16 million cubic meters (FAO and Encyclopedia Britanica on line, Britanica.com). So there is need to find the alternative means to meet this challenge. There is potential area in the arid zone (North-West of India) which is proposed to be covered with Date-Palm grooves¹.

In Italy, there are some grooves of date palms maintained solely to supply the young leaves for religious use on Palm Sunday. In Spain, only the leaves of male palms are utilized for this purpose. In north Africa, the leaves have been commonly used for making huts. Mature leaves are made into mats, screens, baskets, crates and fans. The processed leaflets, combined with ground up peanut shells and corn cobs, are used for making insulating board. The leaf petioles have been found to be good source of cellulose pulp. The leaf sheaths have been prized for their scent. Fibre from old leaf sheaths is used for various

purposes including packsaddles, rope, coarse cloth and large hats. It has been tested as material for filtering drainage pipes in Iraq, as a substitute for imported filters². There is very few publications related to the utilization of DPL fibres³. But in India, no research work has ever been done on development of particle board from Date-Palm Leaves and its commercialization for making false ceiling, furniture, partition wall, window and door panels, table top, bed etc. as a viable substitute of costly wood/plywood board and jute stick particle boards. Only National Institute of Research on Jute & Allied Fibre Technology, Kolkata under Indian Council of Agricultural Research has successfully worked on this type of new technology based products.

Materials and methods :

Matured Date-Palm leaves (DPL) of 60 days' old were air dried for 7 days. The dried leaves were cut to small pieces (½'' to 1'') and chopped/ground in a grinding machine. The chopped leaves particles (of 40–60 mesh size) after uniform mixing with synthetic polymer resin (urea-formaldehyde and phenol-formaldehyde) of different concentrations (10%, 15%, 20% and 25%) in an electric U-Trough mixture fitted with the sigma type blade were transferred in a square mould which was supported

with smooth aluminum plates on both sides and transferred in a hydraulic press. The optimum temperature 160 °C, pressure 20 kg/cm² and time 15 min were maintained. The pressure was released and the board was then taken out hot and allowed to cool. After it had been cooled, the board was edge-finished by electric sawing and stored for conditioning. In the second phase of development of the particle board, the jute stick was ground in machine using (80–100) mesh size of plate. DPL chips were blended with JS in the ratio (DPL : JS :: 75 : 25). Thereafter the blended raw materials mixed with two thermosetting resins (UF and PF) and particle board was developed in the same process as stated above. A few particle boards were treated with water repellent chemicals (1.5% paraffin wax) during mixing resins with ground raw materials. The processing of flow chart for the development of particle board has been computed in Fig. 1. Hydraulic press with multiple day-light are available to make the particle-board on an industrial scale. The plates of the hydraulic press can

be heated electrically or by the steam, but each plate should be maintained at the same temperature. For the development of the particle board of size (10'' × 10'' × ½'') in the Laboratory scale, the electrical heating was found to be economical but for the production of the commercial size of (2' × 2' × ½'') and (4' × 2' × 1') of particle board, steam heating is recommended as more economical. A commercial trial was conducted to develop the particle board from Date-Palm Leaves (size 2' × 2' × ½'') in an industrial unit of Burdwan District of West Bengal and successfully developed 35 Pcs. of particle boards. The false ceiling of room No. 1 of the Trainees' Hostel of the National Institute of Research on Jute & Allied Fibre Technology, Kolkata was fitted with DPL particle boards.

Results and discussion

The chemical compositions of different raw materials (lignocellulosic fibres) are recorded in Table 1⁴⁻⁷.

The chemical compositions of wood (hard and soft),

Fig. 1. Processing flow chart of Date-Palm Leaf Particle.

Table 1. Composition of different raw materials (%)

Constiuents	Date-Palm Leaves (DPL)	Jute Stick	Bagasse	Hard Wood	Soft Wood
α-Cellulose	58.0	40.8	54.5	40.43	40.43
Hemicellulose	20.0	31.9	24.5	30.35	25.30
Lignin	15.3	23.5	20.0	20.25	25.30
Ash	1.75	0.70	1.17	-	-
Others	3.00	3.00	0.33	-	-

jute stick fibre are more or less similar to Date-Palm Leaf fibre but α -cellulose of DPL fibre⁴ is much higher (Table 1). The ultimate fibre length of DPL, wood and JS are (1.25–2.50 mm), (0.4–0.9 mm) and (0.2–0.4 mm) respectively. The α -cellulose and ultimate fibre are the key factors for development of quality particle boards.

The comparative physico-mechanical properties of particle boards from (a) to (d) :

- (a) DPL, JS and DPL : JS (75 : 25) with UF resin
- (b) DPL, JS and DPL : JS (75 : 25) with PF resin
- (c) DPL, JS and wood board with PF resin
- (d) DPL, JS and wood board with UF resin.

have been presented in Tables 2–5 respectively.

From Tables 2 and 3, it appears that incorporation of jute stick powder with DPL in the ratio (75 : 25) with UF resin, the magnitudes of mechanical properties⁵ are increased and swelling percentage in water for 24 h is decreased. The impact strength increased about 100% and swelling percentage decreased by 8% whereas after gradual treatment with water repellent chemical, the swelling percentage gradually decreased. The mechanical properties reflected greater values when the blended DPL, particle boards are made with PF resin. From Tables 4 and 5, the impact strength, tensile strength of particle board made from 100% DPL showed greater values than similar type wood board and jute stick particle board. PF resin treated particle board always exhibits higher magnitude of mechanical properties and lower swelling % in water. It presumes that PF resin is very effective to enhance me-

Table 2. Comparative physico-mechanical properties of Particle Boards from Date-Palm Leaves (DPL), Jute Stick (JS) and DPL : JS (75 : 25)

	Date-Palm Leaf (DPL)				Jute Stick (JS)				DPL : JS (75 : 25)			
	Particle Board				Particle Board				Particle Board			
	10%	15%	20%	25%	10%	15%	20%	25%	10%	15%	20%	25%
UF Resin (synthetic)	10%	15%	20%	25%	10%	15%	20%	25%	10%	15%	20%	25%
Density (g/cm ³)	0.35	0.42	0.58	0.65	0.29	0.38	0.48	0.56	0.28	0.39	0.47	0.51
Average thickness (mm)	12.00	12.08	12.00	12.01	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.01	12.00	12.11	12.12	12.08
Swelling (%) in water (24 h)	6.00	5.16	4.05	4.11	14.41	11.50	11.01	10.95	4.68	4.60	4.58	4.51
Impact strength (kgf.cm)	8.55	8.74	8.92	9.01	3.58	4.17	4.82	5.01	18.64	19.92	19.99	20.01
Tensile strength (N/mm ²)	3.82	3.95	4.01	3.99	1.76	2.05	2.50	2.98	5.22	5.41	5.49	5.41
Swelling (%) after treatment with 0.5% (paraffin wax) as water repellent chemical	2.21	2.05	1.69	2.50	3.82	3.71	3.01	2.85	1.88	1.76	1.58	1.61

Table 3. Comparative physico-mechanical properties of Particle Boards from Date-Palm Leaves (DPL), Jute Stick (JS) and DPL : JS (75 : 25)

	Date-Palm Leaf (DPL)				Jute Stick (JS)				DPL : JS (75 : 25)			
	Particle Board				Particle Board				Particle Board			
	10%	15%	20%	25%	10%	15%	20%	25%	10%	15%	20%	25%
UF Resin (synthetic)	10%	15%	20%	25%	10%	15%	20%	25%	10%	15%	20%	25%
Density (g/cm ³)	0.35	0.42	0.58	0.65	0.29	0.38	0.48	0.56	0.28	0.39	0.47	0.51
Average thickness (mm)	12.00	12.08	12.00	12.01	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.01	12.00	12.11	12.12	12.08
Swelling (%) in water (24 h)	6.00	5.16	4.05	4.11	14.41	11.50	11.01	10.95	4.68	4.60	4.58	4.51
Impact strength (kgf.cm)	8.55	8.74	8.92	9.01	3.58	4.17	4.82	5.01	18.64	19.92	19.99	20.01
Tensile strength (N/mm ²)	3.82	3.95	4.01	3.99	1.76	2.05	2.50	2.98	5.22	5.41	5.49	5.41
Swelling (%) after treatment with 1.5% (paraffin wax) as water repellent chemical	1.83	1.75	1.61	1.60	3.03	2.95	2.87	2.97	1.72	1.61	1.59	1.52

Table 4. Comparative physico-mechanical properties of Particle Boards from Date-Palm Leaves, Jute Stick (JS) and Wood

	Date-Palm Leaf (DPL)				Jute Stick (JS)				Wood
	Particle Board				Particle Board				
UF Resin (synthetic)	10%	15%	20%	25%	10%	15%	20%	25%	No resin used
Density (g/cm ³)	0.35	0.42	0.58	0.65	0.29	0.38	0.48	0.56	0.31
Average thickness (mm)	12.00	12.08	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.01	12.00	12.02
Swelling (%) in water (24 h)	6.00	5.16	4.05	4.11	14.41	11.50	11.01	10.95	9.08
Impact strength (kgf.cm)	8.55	8.74	8.92	9.01	3.58	4.17	4.82	5.01	6.90
Tensile strength (N/mm ²)	3.82	3.95	4.01	3.99	1.76	2.05	2.50	2.98	3.05
Swelling (%) after treatment with 1.5% (paraffin wax) as water repellent chemical	1.83	1.75	1.61	1.60	3.03	2.95	2.87	2.97	4.10

Table 5. Comparative physico-mechanical properties of Particle Boards from Date-Palm Leaves, Jute Stick and Wood

	Date-Palm Leaf (DPL)				Jute Stick (JS)				Wood
	Particle Board				Particle Board				
UF Resin (synthetic)	10%	15%	20%	25%	10%	15%	20%	25%	No resin used
Density (g/cm ³)	0.32	0.47	0.52	0.60	0.25	0.35	0.41	0.40	0.31
Average thickness (mm)	12.00	12.06	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.02
Swelling (%) in water (24 h)	7.00	5.16	4.96	4.50	15.39	13.65	12.39	11.34	9.08
Impact strength (kgf.cm)	7.50	7.90	8.10	8.30	3.50	4.13	4.75	4.92	6.90
Tensile strength (N/mm ²)	3.20	3.35	3.85	4.90	1.41	1.98	2.40	2.99	3.05
Swelling (%) after treatment with 1.5% (paraffin wax) as water repellent chemical	2.21	2.05	1.69	2.50	3.82	3.71	3.01	2.85	4.10

chanical properties and bring down swelling percentage compared to UF resin. The comparative cost structure of particle board and wood board are given in Table 7. It reflects from the table that cost per cft of DPL particle board is about 30% of the cost of wood board. The contact angles of DPL fibre and its blends were measured and computed in Table 6.

The probable reasons of the findings (values computed in Tables 1–6) are the followings :

- (1) (i) The ultimate fibre length (1.5–2.50 mm) of Date-Palm Leaves (*Phoenix Dactylifera-L*) is much higher than that of wood/plywood (0.6–0.9 mm) and jute stick (0.3–0.4 mm) ultimate fibre.

Table 6. Contact angles and work of adhesion of Date-Palm Leaf Fibre and its blends with Jute Stick (in powder from 80–100 mesh size) and comparison with defatted jute using phenol-formaldehyde (PF resin)

Types of fibre	Average diameter of the fibre tested ($D \times 10^{-3}$ mm)	Average contact angle in degree (°)	Cos (θ)	Work of adhesion (WSL)	Work of adhesion per unit perimeter	Type of resin	Surface tension dynes/cm of the resin used
Defatted Jute	14.97	41.00	0.754	85.88	1.83	PF	48.96
Date-Palm Leaf Fibre	13.91	37.00	0.798	88.06	2.016	PF	48.96
Date-Palm Leaf Fibre blended with JS powder	14.05	20.00	0.939	94.93	2.150	PF	48.96

Table 7. Comparative cost structure of Particle Board and Wood Board

Date-Palm Leaf Particle Board	Jute Stick Board	Wood Board
Rs./Cft.	Rs./Cft.	Rs./Cft.
120.00	180.00	500.00

(ii) The α -cellulose content of matured (60 days' of age) Date-Palm Leaves (DPL) is around 60% whereas the α -cellulose content of wood/plywood and jute stick are 41% and 40% respectively. α -Cellulose content and ultimate fibre length are the keys to develop quality board.

- (2) The contact angle between thermosetting resins (UF and PF) and ground up DPL is low and as a result, the work of interfacial adhesion between resin and ground up Date-Palm Leaves (of 40–60 mesh size of plate) registered higher value. Higher mechanical properties of DPL particle board were obtained compared to wood/plywood board and jute stick particle board of same dimensions.
- (3) The interfacial bonding between ground up Date-Palm Leaves and resin may be further improved just by incorporation of organic powder of agricultural by product (agro-waste) which act as filler and confer enhanced mechanical characteristics. Impact strength of Date-Palm Leaf exhibited 4 times higher than jute stick particle board and two times higher than wood/plywood board. These very effective properties are suitable for making furniture and other value added products.
- (4) Moisture content of particle board/wood/plywood plays an important role for dimensional stability of particle board⁹. Hemicelluloses are mainly responsible for moisture sorption because cell wall polymer of fibre of particle board contains hydroxy and oxygen containing groups that attract moisture through hydrogen bonding. Date-Palm Leaves possess low percentage of hemicellulose (about 50% less) compared to wood/plywood and jute stick fibre cellulose.
- (5) Wood/plywood board and jute stick particle board contain distribution of voids/porosity of different shape¹⁰. Water, air, resin fill the voids, surface cracks and debonded the interface. Mechanical and other

properties deteriorate. But in case of DPL particle boards developed with fillers and resin, the possibility of deterioration is very thin.

Conclusions :

India can boast of enjoying pre eminent position in the world for highest production of many natural fibres and agro wastes. DPL (Phoenix Dactylifera-L) is biodegradable, eco-friendly and annually renewable agro-waste. It is abundantly available in India and left unused since long back. No research work and commercialization of the agro-waste have ever been done in India and abroad. National Institute of Research on Jute & Allied Fibre Technology, Kolkata (India) has successfully developed Date-Palm Leaf particle board in commercial scale.

Water repellency, fire-proof, moisture proof properties of DPL particle board may be varied during the development of the board which cannot be possible for the costly wood materials. Regarding cost, it is cheaper by 70% to wood at the present moment. So it may be presumed that it's a noble and new technology and the rural sector can be benefited in generating employment. Even if a part of this abundant supply of agro-waste can replace some of the conventional wood materials, it will be a great boost to the national and international economy. If the new ecofriendly technology for the production of particle board from Date-Palm Leaves is adopted, it will reduce the importing of wood and thus will ensure the savings of foreign exchange.

Acknowledgement

Authors are grateful to Dr. S. K. Bhattacharyya, Director, NIRJAFT for providing with all the facilities and constant encouragement to carry out the research work.

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